

ISO 14001 Certifications in the Global Innovation Index

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The variable measures the value of ISO 14001 certificates in relation to a country's Gross Domestic Product (GDP), calculated in terms of Purchasing Power Parity (PPP) per billion dollars. ISO 14001 is an international standard for environmental management, which sets criteria for creating a management system aimed at improving an organization's environmental performance. A higher number of certificates indicates a broader commitment by companies to sustainable practices and responsible management of environmental impact. This indicator helps assess the effectiveness and spread of environmental policies in a country, as well as the level of awareness and implementation of sustainable practices by businesses. Relating the number of certificates to GDP (PPP) takes into account the economic size of the country, providing a standardized and globally comparable measure. A country with a high value for this variable has an economy in which businesses more frequently adopt certified environmental management systems relative to the size of its economy. In terms of innovation, a high value in this indicator may suggest that the country is making significant progress in integrating sustainability and innovation, while also enhancing global competitiveness through environmentally responsible business practices. Therefore, this indicator reflects the capacity of an economy to balance economic growth and environmental responsibility.

ISO 14001 Certifications in the Global Innovation Index in 2022. The analysis of data related to the density of ISO 14001 environmental certificates in relation to GDP at purchasing power parity (PPP\$) for 2023 reveals a diverse and interesting global picture. The ISO 14001 certification represents an international standard for environmental management systems, aimed at improving the efficiency and sustainability of business operations. By analyzing the data on this certification across different countries, we can identify significant differences in the adoption of environmental management practices relative to their economic capacity. This analysis allows us to explore the relationship between environmental sustainability and economic development, as well as the level of maturity of various industrial and national systems regarding the integration of environmental policies. At the top of the ranking, we find Bosnia and Herzegovina, with a value of 100 ISO 14001 certificates per billion PPP\$. This figure underscores the significant commitment of the country to promoting high environmental management standards, despite its relatively small economy. Bosnia and Herzegovina stands out from many other European and global economies for its high certificate density, indicating a strong focus on sustainability. This result could be linked to local initiatives or policies that encourage the adoption of sustainable environmental practices, possibly tied to the country's proximity or aspirations to join the European Union, which has stringent environmental regulations.

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Another aspect could be the role of the industrial sector, which often adopts certified environmental management systems to improve efficiency and secure access to foreign markets with high standards. Serbia, Bulgaria, Montenegro, and North Macedonia follow Bosnia and Herzegovina with respective values of 79.3, 77.3, 76.3, and 68.1. These Balkan countries also show a significant spread of ISO 14001 certificates. The adoption of certified environmental standards could be driven by various factors, including the need to attract foreign investments, improve corporate image, and increase environmental awareness both at the business and consumer levels. Additionally, obtaining ISO 14001 certification is often a requirement to access more regulated international markets, such as the European one. The presence of countries such as Estonia, Slovakia, Croatia, and Czechia in the subsequent positions, with values between 64 and 57.4, indicates that even in Central and Northern Europe, attention to environmental management is quite high. These countries, which are part of or close to the European Union, have benefited from EU policies that incentivize sustainable practices and international certifications. Economic integration with EU countries, where environmental regulations are advanced, has likely pushed these nations to adopt high standards to remain competitive in global markets. Italy's position is also interesting, with a value of 44.9 certificates per billion PPP\$, placing it in an intermediate position among European countries. Despite having an advanced and industrialized economy, Italy appears to have a slightly lower adoption of ISO 14001 certificates compared to other European economies. This could be due to various factors, including the fragmentation of the Italian industrial fabric, which is characterized by a prevalence of small and medium-sized enterprises (SMEs) that may find it more difficult to implement certified environmental management systems compared to large multinational corporations. However, Italy's commitment to sustainability is growing, partly thanks to public incentives and the increasing demand from consumers for more eco-friendly products and services. Continuing the analysis, China, one of the world's largest economies, has a value of 42.9. This figure reflects an interesting evolution in China's environmental policy. In recent years, China has invested heavily in sustainability, both at the government policy level and through industrial initiatives. However, the vastness of the Chinese economy and the rapid pace of industrial growth may explain why the number of ISO 14001 certificates relative to PPP GDP is not exceptionally high. Nevertheless, China represents a notable case of a country seeking to balance economic growth with more rigorous environmental management practices. As we move down the rankings, we find advanced economies like the United Kingdom (24.6), Norway (24.6), and Switzerland (22.3) with relatively low values. This may seem surprising considering the strong environmental commitment of these countries. However, a plausible explanation is that in these contexts, many companies may adopt high environmental standards without necessarily seeking ISO 14001 certification. In countries with strong internal regulations and a culture of sustainability, many businesses follow advanced environmental management practices even without formalizing these practices through international certifications. The presence of other national or European standards may also compete with the widespread adoption of ISO 14001. Another interesting element to consider is the relatively low position of countries like the United States (1 certificate per billion PPP\$), Canada (2.7), and Australia (14). Although these are highly developed economies, the low density of ISO 14001 certificates could be due to the predominance of other environmental or management standards, or to a lesser emphasis on formal certifications compared to other parts of the world. In the United States, for example, companies may be more inclined to follow customized or sector-specific environmental standards rather than obtain a specific certification like ISO 14001. On the opposite end of the spectrum, we find countries like Burundi (2.6), Mozambique (2.1), Botswana (1.7), and many other developing countries with very low values, often below 2 certificates per billion PPP\$. This is not surprising, as many of these nations are still developing their economic and industrial infrastructures, and the adoption of certified environmental management standards may not be a priority compared to more immediate economic and social

challenges. In many of these contexts, the implementation of environmental management systems may be hindered by a lack of resources, technical knowledge, or economic incentives. However, as economic conditions improve and access to new markets becomes available, these countries may begin to place greater emphasis on ISO 14001 certification. In summary, the analysis of the data on the spread of ISO 14001 certificates reveals several key trends. Countries with a higher density of certificates tend to be European or Balkan nations, which, despite having less developed economies compared to giants like the United States or China, show significant commitment to sustainability. Advanced economies often have a lower density of certificates, but this could reflect the presence of other forms of environmental management or internal standards rather than a lack of commitment. Finally, in developing countries, the low adoption of ISO 14001 certificates indicates that the implementation of certified environmental management systems may not yet be a priority, although this trend could change with economic progress and greater integration into global markets.

ISO 14001 Certifications in the Global Innovation Index between 2013 and 2022. The analysis of data related to ISO 14001 environmental certificates per billion GDP in purchasing power parity (PPP\$) shows a significant variation in the spread of these certificates between 2013 and 2022. The ISO 14001 certification represents an international standard for environmental management, helping organizations improve the sustainability of their operations and reduce their environmental impact. Changes in the density of these certificates relative to each country's economy are a relevant indicator of the adoption of sustainable practices and growing environmental awareness. One of the most surprising cases is Ghana, which saw a 2300% increase, going from 0.1 to 2.4 certificates per billion GDP. This growth demonstrates an exponential rise in the adoption of certified environmental management systems. Although the absolute value remains low compared to countries with more developed economies, the increase is still significant and reflects a growing interest in sustainability and environmental management in Ghana. This change could be the result of governmental or international initiatives aimed at promoting sustainable development practices, particularly in emerging economies like Ghana's. Another country that has shown extraordinary growth is Albania, with an increase of 678.13%, rising from 3.2 to 24.9 certificates per billion GDP. Albania has likely benefited from international pressures and its proximity to the European Union, which has very strict environmental standards. The adoption of environmental management policies may also be part of a strategy to attract foreign investment, as international companies tend to prefer operating in countries with clear and well-managed environmental regulations. Mali and Jamaica saw increases of 366.67% and 296.3%, respectively, also indicating an improvement in the adoption of environmental management practices. In countries like Mali, where economic development is still in its early stages, these data suggest that even less developed economies are beginning to take sustainability seriously. However, the increase in countries like Jamaica may be explained by the tourism sector, which is highly sensitive to environmental issues and may have been incentivized to obtain certifications to improve its international reputation. Countries like Belarus, Qatar, Morocco, and Oman have also shown notable increases in the density of ISO 14001 certificates, with growth rates ranging between 200% and 280%. These countries have likely adopted more stringent regulations or initiated sustainable development programs, driven by a combination of external pressures, such as international climate agreements, and the need to make their industrial sectors more sustainable. In particular, Qatar and Oman, which heavily rely on the oil and gas industry, may have sought to improve their international image through the adoption of more responsible environmental practices. On the other hand, some countries have shown a significant decrease in the density of ISO 14001 certificates. Among them, South Korea (-72.39%), Japan (-59.88%), Canada (-69.32%), and Singapore (-68.68%) stand out. A possible explanation for this trend is that in these countries, many companies may have already implemented the necessary environmental management practices and no longer see ISO 14001 certification as a priority. There may also be competition between different certification standards, with some companies opting for national or sectoral alternatives, thus

reducing the spread of ISO 14001. Moreover, highly developed economies might be focusing on other aspects of environmental management, such as technological innovation and energy efficiency, rather than specific certifications. Another notable example of decline is Romania and Czechia, which saw reductions of 44.6% and 42.6%, respectively. Countries like Italy (-48.27%) and Spain (-49.83%) have also registered significant declines. These data may indicate a perceived reduced need to obtain ISO 14001 certification, especially if domestic or community regulations already provide strong incentives to improve environmental practices. Additionally, the presence of European regulations offering comprehensive regulatory frameworks may have reduced the reliance on specific certifications like ISO 14001. Another group of countries with significant declines includes the United States (-58.33%) and Switzerland (-57.28%). Despite being highly developed economies, the adoption of ISO 14001 certification has drastically decreased. In the United States, for example, the decline may be attributed to a more flexible regulatory context in environmental matters or a preference for internal standards. Moreover, the private sector in the U.S. may have a stronger focus on innovation rather than certification, choosing to invest in sustainable technologies over environmental management standards. The case of Sweden, which saw a 61.02% decline, is particularly surprising given the country's image as a global leader in sustainability. Here, too, it is possible that Swedish companies have opted for other standards or have already reached such high levels of environmental management that further certifications are unnecessary. Finally, it is worth mentioning countries like Estonia (-36.00%) and Latvia (-37.55%), which recorded significant reductions. These countries, despite a strong push towards economic modernization and the adoption of sustainable practices, may have been affected by economic issues or market saturation for certifications. It is possible that companies that needed ISO 14001 certification had already obtained it in previous years, leading to a reduction in demand for new certifications. In conclusion, the analysis of ISO 14001 certification data between 2013 and 2022 shows a wide range of variations across countries and regions. While many developing countries have shown impressive growth in the adoption of these standards, many advanced economies have recorded significant declines. This reflects both the evolution of environmental regulations and the maturity of environmental management systems in each country. For some countries, obtaining the certification remains a priority to improve their image and attract investments, while for others, ISO 14001 certification has been replaced by other strategies or standards.

Economic Policies. The promotion of ISO 14001 certification in relation to Gross Domestic Product (GDP) at Purchasing Power Parity (PPP\$) requires a set of integrated and targeted economic policies that encourage businesses to adopt environmental standards. ISO 14001 certification is a recognized international standard that provides a framework for environmental management systems, helping organizations reduce their environmental impact and improve operational performance through more efficient resource management. Widespread adoption of this standard can bring benefits to both businesses and the broader economy by improving sustainability, reducing operating costs, and increasing competitiveness in the global market. To promote the spread of this certification, governments and institutions need to implement a range of economic policies that incentivize businesses to pursue environmental sustainability goals. One of the first measures governments can take is to create tax incentives for companies that implement ISO 14001 certification. These tax benefits can take various forms, such as tax credits, deductions, or exemptions for companies that adopt certified environmental management standards. This type of economic policy reduces the initial cost for businesses, particularly for small and medium-sized enterprises (SMEs), which may find it difficult to bear the costs of certification implementation. In this way, governments can promote the adoption of ISO 14001 in strategic sectors of the economy and facilitate the achievement of national sustainability goals. In addition to tax incentives, governments can introduce favorable financing programs for businesses that wish to obtain ISO 14001 certification. These programs could include

zero or low-interest loans for companies investing in environmental management systems and green technologies. In particular, governments could collaborate with public or private banks to create special funds dedicated to promoting sustainable practices within businesses. These financial instruments would not only facilitate access to the capital needed for the adoption of ISO 14001 but also strengthen companies' long-term commitment to improving their environmental performance. Another effective approach to encouraging ISO 14001 adoption is the introduction of stricter environmental regulations, where compliance with certified environmental management standards becomes mandatory for certain industrial sectors or companies operating in specific fields. For example, the government could mandate that all companies in the manufacturing or energy sectors obtain ISO 14001 certification within a specified period. This type of regulation can be combined with a transition period that allows businesses to adapt and prepare to meet the new requirements without facing overly burdensome economic impacts. Such a regulatory approach would stimulate a significant increase in certifications, especially in more polluting sectors, and improve the overall sustainability of the national economy. Economic policies aimed at promoting the spread of ISO 14001 certification can also include strengthening public-private partnerships. The government can work closely with industrial associations, chambers of commerce, non-governmental organizations (NGOs), and academic institutions to raise awareness among businesses about the benefits of ISO 14001 certification. These collaborations could lead to the development of specific training programs for executives and business leaders on environmental management practices and the implementation of ISO 14001 standards. By offering training and technical advice, the government can help companies overcome any technical or knowledge barriers that prevent them from adopting certified environmental standards. Additionally, public-private collaboration can facilitate the exchange of best practices among companies and contribute to creating a more sustainability-oriented business culture. Another useful economic strategy is the inclusion of ISO 14001 certification as a criterion for accessing public procurement tenders or securing contracts with the government. This type of measure would ensure that only companies meeting certain environmental standards can compete to provide goods and services to the public sector. Such a policy could have a significant impact, as the public sector represents a substantial portion of the economy in many countries. The inclusion of environmental criteria in procurement would encourage companies to pursue ISO 14001 certification to improve their business opportunities, leading to increased competitiveness among businesses and, consequently, greater adoption of sustainable practices. At the same time, governments can encourage the private sector to seek ISO 14001 certification through public awareness campaigns and environmental labeling programs. Environmental marketing campaigns that promote the benefits of consuming products and services offered by ISO 14001 certified companies can increase consumer demand for sustainable goods and services. Environmental labeling, which clearly identifies products that meet sustainability standards, can positively influence purchasing decisions and create a competitive advantage for certified companies. Furthermore, these campaigns may also push businesses that have not yet adopted the ISO 14001 standard to do so, to avoid losing market share to more sustainable competitors. Economic policies may also include strengthening international agreements on climate and environmental standards. Compliance with stricter international environmental regulations may encourage companies to adopt ISO 14001 certification to maintain compliance with laws and regulations. Governments can work to incorporate ISO 14001 certification into the regulatory frameworks of international organizations, making it a requirement for operating in global markets. In this way, companies looking to expand internationally will be motivated to obtain certification to access new markets and comply with local laws. Another policy measure could be encouraging the adoption of ISO 14001 certification through corporate social responsibility (CSR) programs. Governments could recognize and reward companies that stand out for their environmental performance with certificates of excellence, additional tax benefits, or visibility on institutional platforms. This type of recognition not only values companies that adopt sustainable practices but also encourages them to continue on this path, while also fostering virtuous competition among businesses. Finally, to ensure that economic policies effectively promote the adoption of ISO 14001

certification, governments must also develop mechanisms for monitoring and evaluating companies' environmental performance. The introduction of clear and measurable environmental performance indicators can help monitor companies' progress and identify areas where further intervention is needed. Additionally, governments can collaborate with businesses to develop reporting tools that allow for transparent communication of environmental performance, improving the accountability of sustainable activities. In summary, economic policies to promote ISO 14001 certification must be integrated and multifactorial. Tax incentives, favorable financing, strict regulations, public-private partnerships, environmental criteria in public procurement, environmental labeling, and awareness campaigns are all measures that can contribute to increasing the spread of ISO 14001 certification. These policies not only foster greater environmental sustainability but also improve companies' competitiveness in the global market, creating a greener and more responsible economic environment.

Conclusions. The value of the analyzed variable has significantly decreased on average from 2013 to 2022, dropping from an amount of 18.88 to a value of 15.92, representing a decline of -15.69%. There are some countries where this value has significantly increased over the period considered, such as Ghana with +2300.00%, Albania with 678.13%, Mali with +366.67%, Jamaica with +296.30%, and Belarus with +280.65%. There are also countries where this value has decreased, such as Armenia with -68.75%, Canada with -69.32%, South Korea with -72.39%, the Dominican Republic with -76.47%, and Zambia with -76.47%.

	Countries	2013	2022	Var Ass	Var Per
Top Players	Ghana	0,1	2,4	2,3	2300,00
	Albania	3,2	24,9	21,7	678,13
	Mali	0,3	1,4	1,1	366,67
	Jamaica	2,7	10,7	8	296,30
	Belarus	3,1	11,8	8,7	280,65
Worse Players	Armenia	1,6	0,5	-1,1	-68,75
	Canada	8,8	2,7	-6,1	-69,32
	Korea, Rep.	53,6	14,8	-38,8	-72,39
	Dominican Republic	3,4	0,8	-2,6	-76,47
	Zambia	3,4	0,8	-2,6	-76,47

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